

Extending and measuring dephasing times of nuclear spins in NV centers of diamond

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Long coherence times rank among the most important performance measures for many different types of quantum technology. In NV centers of diamond, the nuclear spins provide particularly long dephasing times. However, since initialization and readout require assistance from the electron spin, the apparent dephasing times can be reduced by the electron spin lifetime. Here we propose and implement schemes for measuring and extending the dephasing times of nuclear spins, resulting in dephasing times that are longer than the longitudinal relaxation time T_1 of the electron spin.

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Introduction.—In all areas of quantum technologies like quantum computing and quantum sensing [1], the preservation of quantum information in the presence of a noisy environment is one of the most challenging tasks. Hybrid systems such as nitrogen-vacancy (NV) centers in diamond are promising for implementing quantum computing [2–6], which is believed to have a large potential for speeding up the solution of certain problems that have no easy solutions for classical computers. One of the main benefits of the NV system lies in the long coherence time of the nuclear spins, e.g., up to one minute at low temperature (3.7 K) [7].

However, the preservation and measurement of the coherence, are limited by the longitudinal relaxation time (T_1^e) of the electron spin [8–10]. Specifically, if the electron spin changes its state as a result of longitudinal (T_1^e) relaxation, the connected nuclear spin experiences a different hyperfine coupling, which results in the loss of its coherence. In addition, the detection of the coherence of the nuclear spin depends on the polarization of the electron spin and the loss of this polarization due to longitudinal relaxation reduces the measured coherence time [8, 9]. In this letter, we relax these limitations in two ways: During the coherence storage period, we partially refocus the nuclear spin coherence with a Hahn echo. In addition, we modify the detection scheme: instead of measuring the coherence of the nuclear spin in only one subspace of the electron state [5, 8], we exchange the states of nuclear spin and the electron spin using a SWAP gate [2], which transfers the nuclear spin coherence into electronic spin coherence that can be measured through the combination of a $\pi/2$ microwave (MW) pulse and a readout laser pulse. In contrast to earlier work [11] on weakly coupled systems, or based on encoded qubits [12, 13], our current work focuses on a strongly coupled system without ancillary qubits.

System.—We consider a ^{13}C nuclear spin strongly coupled to the electron spin of a single NV center. Here, strong coupling means that the hyperfine coupling is close to the nuclear spin Larmor frequency [14, 15]. Initially, we do not consider the ^{14}N nuclear spin of the NV center but focus onto the subsystem where the ^{14}N is (and remains)

in the $m_N=1$ state. This is a safe assumption since the population lifetime (T_1^N) of the ^{14}N nuclear spin is much longer than that of the electron spin [12, 16]. The spins interact with a weak magnetic field $B \approx 148$ G oriented along the symmetry axis of the NV center. In a suitable reference frame, we can write the relevant part of the Hamiltonian as

$$\frac{1}{2\pi}\mathcal{H}_{e,C} = DS_z^2 - (\nu_e - A_N)S_z - \nu_C I_z + A_{zz}S_z I_z + A_{zx}S_z I_x, \quad (1)$$

where S_z denotes the electron spin-1 operator, and $I_{x/z}$ the ^{13}C spin-1/2 operators. The zero-field splitting is $D = 2.87$ GHz. $\nu_{e/C} = \gamma_{e/C}B$ denote the Larmor frequencies of the spins specified by the indices for the electron and ^{13}C nuclear spins, with γ being the gyromagnetic ratio. $A_N = -2.16$ MHz is the secular part of the hyperfine coupling with the ^{14}N nuclear spin while A_{zz} and A_{zx} are the relevant components of the ^{13}C hyperfine tensor. We measured $\nu_C = 0.158$, $A_{zz} = -0.152$ and $A_{zx} = 0.110$ MHz [14]. These values are highly suitable for indirect control of the nuclear spin [15, 17–19].

In the experiment, we used a ^{12}C enriched diamond as the sample, which provides a long coherence time of the electron spin ($T_2^{*e} \approx 35$ μs). The experiment was performed at room temperature. In the following, we write $|m_S\rangle$ for the eigenstate of S_z with eigenvalue m_S , and $|\uparrow\rangle$ and $|\downarrow\rangle$ for the eigenstates of I_z with eigenvalues $\pm 1/2$.

To prepare the system for the measurement, we use a combination of laser and MW pulses [14, 15] to initialize the system into the state

$$\rho_{ini}^{e,C} = s_1|0\uparrow\rangle\langle 0\uparrow| + (1-s_1)|1\downarrow\rangle\langle 1\downarrow| \quad (2)$$

with $s_1 = 0.80$. The first term is used to generate the coherence of the nuclear spin. The second term results from the imperfection in polarizing the ^{13}C spin and contributes observable effects in the detected signals. Details of the pulse sequence for preparing $\rho_{ini}^{e,C}$ are given in the supplementary material (SM, Sect. IIB).

FIG. 1: Quantum circuits for measuring the dephasing of the ^{13}C spin during free precession (a) and with refocusing by a Hahn echo (b). In each circuit, the top line denotes the electron spin qubit and the bottom the ^{13}C spin. The initial state is $|0, \uparrow\rangle$. H represents a Hadamard gate, 180_x the refocusing pulse and SWAP the 2-qubit SWAP gate. The filled rectangles indicate the readout laser pulses.

Experimental protocol and results.—Fig. 1 shows the protocol for the relaxation measurement of the ^{13}C spin as quantum circuits for the free induction decay (FID) (a) and the Hahn-echo (b). Here, we only consider the 4-level subsystem with the initial state corresponding to the first term in Eq. (2). In this subsystem, we use unitary operations that correspond to a Hadamard gate H and refocusing pulse 180_x to ^{13}C spin, and the two-qubit SWAP gate. All these operations were implemented without RF pulses, using indirect control for the ^{13}C spin [14, 15]. The final 90_ϕ readout pulse converts a component of the electron spin coherence into observable population of the electron spin. Its phase ϕ is incremented in proportion to the free precession time τ : $\phi = 2\pi\nu_d\tau + \phi_0$, where ϕ_0 denotes an initial phase. As a result, the observed signal oscillates at frequency $\nu_s = \nu_C + \nu_d$ (ν_d) in the FID (Hahn-echo) experiment. The detuning frequency ν_d was chosen as $\nu_d^a = -0.5$ MHz in (a) and as $\nu_d^b = \nu_d^a + \nu_C$ in (b), respectively, so that the measured signals from circuits (a) and (b) have the same frequency $\nu_s = 0.342$ MHz, to allow easier comparison, as illustrated in Figure 2. The state of the electron qubit can be detected by laser pulses, as shown in Fig. 1 [5].

Applying the Hadamard gate H to the ^{13}C spin generates the superposition state $|+\rangle = (|\uparrow\rangle + |\downarrow\rangle)/\sqrt{2}$ from $|\uparrow\rangle$. Therefore $\rho_{ini}^{e,C}$ shown in Eq. (2) is transformed to

$$\rho_{sup}^{e,C} = s_1|0\rangle\langle 0| \otimes |+\rangle\langle +| + (1 - s_1)|1\downarrow\rangle\langle 1\downarrow|, \quad (3)$$

where the state of the ^{13}C spin in the subspace of electron state $|1\rangle$ remains unchanged by the Hadamard gate H . We discuss the cases of FID and Hahn echo in the following.

In the FID experiment shown in Fig. 1(a), the nuclear spin coherence is allowed to undergo free evolution for a time τ . The coherence evolves continuously and dephases under the effect of environmental perturbations. These perturbations include the longitudinal relaxation of the electron spin (T_1^e): If it flips between states $|0\rangle$ and $| - 1\rangle$ ($|1\rangle$), the nuclear spin coherence prepared

between $|0, \uparrow\rangle \leftrightarrow |0, \downarrow\rangle$, with precession frequency $\nu_0 = \nu_C = 0.158$ MHz, is transferred to the $| - 1, \uparrow\rangle \leftrightarrow | - 1, \downarrow\rangle$ ($|1, \uparrow\rangle \leftrightarrow |1, \downarrow\rangle$) transition, where it precesses with a different frequency $\nu_{-1} = \sqrt{A_{zx}^2 + (\nu_C + A_{zz})^2} = 0.110$ MHz ($\nu_1 = \sqrt{A_{zx}^2 + (\nu_C - A_{zz})^2} = 0.329$ MHz). Since this transfer is an incoherent process, the coherence of the nuclear spins coupled to the $m_S = \pm 1$ electron spin subsystems vanishes.

We denote the populations of the different electron spin levels as $P_{m_S}(\tau)$, and write the state at the end of the evolution period as

$$\rho_{FID}^{e,C}(\tau) = \sum_{m_S} P_{m_S}(\tau) (|m_S\rangle\langle m_S|) \otimes \varrho_{FID}^{C_{m_S}}(\tau) \quad (4)$$

where $\varrho_{FID}^{C_{m_S}}(\tau)$ denotes the nuclear spin state in the subspace $|m_S\rangle$ of the electron spin, and

$$P_0(\tau) = \frac{1}{3} - 2\left(\frac{1}{6} - \frac{s_1}{2}\right)e^{-3\kappa\tau} \quad (5)$$

$$P_{-1}(\tau) = \frac{1}{3} + \left(\frac{1}{6} - \frac{s_1}{2}\right)e^{-3\kappa\tau} - \frac{1}{2}(1 - s_1)e^{-\kappa\tau} \quad (6)$$

$$P_1(\tau) = \frac{1}{3} + \left(\frac{1}{6} - \frac{s_1}{2}\right)e^{-3\kappa\tau} + \frac{1}{2}(1 - s_1)e^{-\kappa\tau} \quad (7)$$

with $T_1^e = 1/(3\kappa)$, where T_1^e is the electron spin relaxation time and its experimental value is 5.5 ms. Details are in Section I of the SM. The state of the nuclear spin in the electron spin subspace $|1\rangle$ does not contribute to the observed signals, since the readout is selective for the subspace $|0\rangle, | - 1\rangle$. In the subspace $m_S = 0$ we have with

$$\varrho_{FID}^{C_0}(\tau) = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & c_{FID}(\tau)e^{-i2\pi\nu_C\tau} \\ c_{FID}(\tau)e^{i2\pi\nu_C\tau} & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

In the following, we assume an exponential decay of the coherence $c_{FID}(\tau) = e^{-\tau/T_2^C}$. More details on Eq. (8) are presented in the SM. The populations $P_{\pm 1}(\tau)$ of the electron spin state $|\pm 1\rangle$ are the result of incoherent (T_1^e) process, and therefore no nuclear spin coherence builds up in these subsystems.

To generate an observable signal from the nuclear spin coherence, we use a 3-step process: we first apply a SWAP operation to the 2-qubit system to convert the nuclear spin coherence into electron spin coherence, then we apply a 90° pulse to the electron and count the fluorescence photons during the readout-laser-pulse [5].

The SWAP operation exchanges the states of the ^{13}C nuclear spin qubit with that of the electron spin qubit. It transforms the state $\rho_{FID}^{e,C}(\tau)$ in Eq. (4) to

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{FID,S}^{e,C}(\tau) &= P_0(\tau)\varrho_{FID}^{C_0}(\tau) \otimes (|\uparrow\rangle\langle\uparrow|) \\ &+ P_{-1}(\tau)E/2 \otimes (|\downarrow\rangle\langle\downarrow|) \\ &+ P_1(\tau)|1\rangle\langle 1| \otimes \varrho_{FID}^{C_1}(\tau). \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Here, $\varrho_{FID}^{C_0}$ is defined in Eq. (8), and E denotes the 2×2 unit operator. The SWAP operation has therefore transferred the coherence $c_{FID}(\tau)$ to the electron spin states. From there, it is converted into a population difference by a 90° MW pulse with a time-dependent phase $\phi = 2\pi\nu_d^a\tau + \phi_0$. Finally, a readout laser pulse measures the population of the electron spin in the state $|0\rangle$,

$$p_{|0\rangle,FID}(\tau) = (1/2)[P_0(\tau) + P_{-1}(\tau) + P_0(\tau)c_{FID}(\tau)\sin(2\pi\nu_s\tau + \phi_0)], \quad (10)$$

where $\nu_s = -(\nu_C + \nu_d^a) = 0.342$ MHz. Here and in the following, p refers to the population after the SWAP operation and the 90° pulse, and P to the population before the SWAP. Figure 2 illustrates the measured $p_{|0\rangle,FID}(\tau)$ for two time segments. More results are listed in the SM.

FIG. 2: Measured signals with the fitted curves for the FID and Hahn-echo.

The signal $p_{|0\rangle,FID}(\tau)$ in Eq. (10) consists of an oscillating part that reflects the coherence in the system, with amplitude $P_0(\tau)c_{FID}(\tau)/2$ and a background $[P_0(\tau) + P_{-1}(\tau)]/2$, which reflects the populations. Fig. 3 shows the experimental results, where we fit the measured background in $p_{|0\rangle,FID}(\tau)$ to the function $[P_0(\tau) + P_{-1}(\tau)]/2 - d_0$ with the offset $d_0 = 0.086$. More details are presented in the SM. By fitting the measured amplitude of the coherence $p_{|0\rangle,FID}(\tau)$ to the function $P_0(\tau)c_{FID}(\tau)/2$, where

$$c_{FID}(\tau) = c_{0,FID}e^{-\tau/T_2^{*C}}, \quad (11)$$

we obtain the dephasing time T_2^{*C} . The experimental results and the corresponding fits are shown in Fig. 3 (bottom), where the amplitude denotes $P_0(\tau)c_{FID}(\tau)/2$ or $[P_0(\tau) + P_{-1}(\tau)]c_{Hahn}(\tau)/2$ for FID or Hahn-echo experiment, respectively. Additional details are given in the SM. In Table I, we list the obtained parameters.

The Hahn-echo experiment starts with the same initialization as the FID experiment but uses an inversion pulse in the middle of the evolution period to partly refocus the evolution, as shown in Fig. 1(b). Additional details are given in the SM. The state at the qubit system at the

FIG. 3: Experimental results for the background $[P_0(\tau) + P_{-1}(\tau)]/2$ (top) and for the oscillation amplitude (bottom) in the FID and Hahn-echo experiments, which measures the nuclear spin coherence.

^{13}C , FID	$c_{0,FID} = 0.80$	$T_2^{*C} = 8.66$ ms
^{13}C , Hahn-echo	$c_{0,Hahn} = 0.76$	$T_2^C = 14.10$ ms

TABLE I: Parameters obtained by fitting the experimental data in Figs. 3 to the function (11). The details on the normalization of the experimental data are presented in Section II of the SM.

end of the full evolution $(\frac{\tau}{2} - 180_x - \frac{\tau}{2})$ and the SWAP operation is

$$\rho_{Hahn,S}^{e,C}(\tau) = \varrho_{Hahn}(\tau) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} P_0(\tau) & 0 \\ 0 & P_{-1}(\tau) \end{pmatrix} + P_1(\tau)|1\rangle\langle 1| \otimes \varrho_{Hahn}^{C_1}(\tau),$$

where the operator

$$\varrho_{Hahn}(\tau) = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & c_{Hahn}(\tau) \\ c_{Hahn}(\tau) & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$c_{Hahn}(\tau) = e^{-\tau/T_2^C}.$$

is now an electron spin operator in the (0,-1) subspace. Similar to the detection in the FID experiment, we apply a 90° pulse with a phase $\phi = 2\pi\nu_d^b\tau + \phi_0$ to obtain the population

$$p_{|0\rangle,Hahn}(\tau) = [P_0(\tau) + P_{-1}(\tau)]/2 \cdot [1 + c_{Hahn}(\tau)\sin(2\pi\nu_d^b\tau + \phi_0)]. \quad (12)$$

Here we choose the detuning frequency as $\nu_d^b = -0.342$ MHz, different from the case of the FID, so that the

resulting oscillation frequencies are the same. The experimental data can then be fitted to $[P_0(\tau) + P_{-1}(\tau)]c_{Hahn}(\tau)/2$, where

$$c_{Hahn}(\tau) = c_{0,Hahn}e^{-\tau/T_2^C}. \quad (13)$$

This allows us to extract T_2 . Table I lists the resulting parameters. They show that the refocusing pulse in the Hahn echo extends the dephasing by 60% compared to the FID.

Eq. (12) shows, that of T_1^e still limits the amplitude of the detected signals in measuring the coherence of the nuclear spin, but the effect is smaller than in the case of the FID experiment, see Eq. (10). Applying echo pulses to the nuclear spin in the subspace of $m_S = 1$ might further relax the limitation.

Conclusion and outlook.— We have measured the dephasing of the ^{13}C nuclear spin in a single NV center during free precession and with partial refocusing in a Hahn echo experiment. Compared with previous works, e.g. [8, 9], we introduced an improved detection scheme for the nuclear spin coherence, which relies on a SWAP gate. In the case of the FID, the nuclear spin dephasing time T_2^* exceeds T_1^e by a factor of 1.6. Using one refocusing pulse, we further extended the coherence time to 2.6 times T_1^e . The effect of electron spin flips between states $|0\rangle$ and $| - 1\rangle$ due to T_1^e relaxation can be suppressed in the fol-

lowing way: In the subspace $|0\rangle$, the echo can refocus the evolution of the nuclear spin, while in subspace $| - 1\rangle$, the nuclear spin can be approximated by an eigenstate of the effective Hamiltonian ($\sim I_x$) and therefore does not evolve. In the present work, we only use one echo on the nuclear spin in a subspace of two states $|0\rangle$ and $| - 1\rangle$ of the electron spin, where indirect control in this subspace. We believe that multiple echos should extend the coherence time further [20, 21], and might provide a useful method to investigate the physics model for T_1^e , where the nuclear spin works as a useful ancillary quantum memory [12, 22, 23]. Our experiment was performed in NV centers. The method should also work in other systems, such as malonic acid radical [18, 24] and other solid defects [25].

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